

WE ARE AGAINST CORRUPTION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7457158>

In the fight against corruption, it is necessary to improve the legal culture, to identify and suppress such crimes as bribery, self-interest, to know that punishment for such crimes is inevitable. Therefore, such events are regularly organized with students and youth.

A person who understands how terrible corruption is, who consciously perceives it, does not commit this crime. Corruption - (lat. "corruptio") - bribery, bribery and corruption of public and political figures, government officials and officials for the purpose of personal enrichment. The historical roots of corruption go back to the custom of giving gifts in order to achieve a good disposition, to achieve a solution to the issue, to speed up its solution.

Corruption is a multi-headed monster. The secret is that here we have a particularly strong fusion of the criminal and the state itself in the person of its representatives, including, even more terrifyingly, law enforcement officials who are called upon to fight corruption. We can only create the appearance of a struggle, issue orders and decrees, make dozens of smart proposals and decisions, even pass individual laws. But if the state itself, in the person of its officials of the highest and highest Echelon, does not really decide on uncompromising steps, all attempts are in vain" wrote S. Ruslanov [1].

The resolution of the 44th UN General Assembly, adopted in 1999 "On international cooperation in the fight against organized crime", notes that it is the "business" relationships between swindlers-dealers of the "black" business, prestigious groups of individual states of the modern world are based on "unwritten laws" of corruption. At the Assembly, it was determined that corruption is "the abuse of official position to achieve personal or group gain, as well as the illegal receipt by public servants of benefits in connection with their official position" [2].

Corruption has a place in the public life of the whole world since ancient times. This disease affected such developed countries as India, China, Athens, and then ancient Rus'. One of the first legislative restrictions known in history for the region in which the CIS countries are now located belongs to Ivan III. And his grandson Ivan the Terrible was the first to introduce the death penalty as a punishment for excessive bribery.

Creating a legal and organizational framework for the fight against corruption in the Soviet Union, Uzbekistan holds the palm. For this purpose, the laws “On Combating Corruption”, “On National Security”, and “On Public Service” were adopted. A code of honor for civil servants has been adopted. A permanent Commission under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the fight against corruption has been created, an authorized body has been identified - the Agency for Combating Economic and Corruption Crimes. The Head of State signed the Law “On Ratification of the UN Convention against Corruption”.

By joining the UN Convention against Corruption, Uzbekistan entered the system of international cooperation, which significantly expanded the possibilities for searching for and extraditing persons who fled from criminal prosecution abroad.

The issue of combating corruption in each of his speeches is given by the President of our state Sh.M. Mirziyoyev.

We must improve the quality of civil service personnel through the introduction of improved selection and training methods.

First of all, the state apparatus will be reformed. I signed the Law on the new civil service system. It ensures the strengthening of anti-corruption measures, increasing the transparency of the selection of civil servants, the introduction of the principle of meritocracy, that is, the promotion of the best personnel" [3]. Corruption has many forms. I would like to make one very important clarification. Corruption is usually understood (both in theory and in practice) only from one side - self-serving and property.

In one Message of the President of the country to the people of Uzbekistan it was said: “Insufficiently trained and poorly organized management should be included among our liabilities. Today, the solution of many problems’ rests on this factor, and it cannot be overcome quickly. So far, we have very few people capable of solving strategic tasks at a highly professional level, patriotically and honestly. Habits of interference in all affairs, departmentalism, dullness, lack of initiative, inadequate and multi-stage structure, corruption - this is the far from complete bouquet of the “qualities” of our bureaucracy” [2].

As Doctor of Law, Professor Isa Khamedov notes: “Political parties should also actively join the fight against corruption, which should use the facts of corruption not for political struggle with other parties, but to consolidate their readership to solve nationwide problems of fighting corruption. That is, the fight against corruption should be the concern not only of the president, but also of other and political leaders who are able to lead the masses in the fight against

corruption, so that their personal impeccability creates a new moral climate in society” [3].

A positive impact on the results of the fight against corruption is exerted by the intensification of the work of anti-corruption public organizations and political parties, in particular the People's Democratic Party of Uzbekistan, which are fruitfully involved in law-making activities, educating the patriotic feelings of the population.

It is necessary to create a new generation of law enforcement officials of the state who have a stable immunity of non-perception of illegal (illegal) self-interest, impeccable devotion to the interests of the service and subordination and service only to the law.

The problem of staffing the fight against corruption must also be solved through the system of special education and scientific research.

It is necessary to study and adopt the experience of the advanced countries of the world. Uzbekistan has the opportunity to improve the legislative framework in the fight against corruption using the example of international experience, and there are examples of applying international experience in the fight against such social evil as corruption.

Thus, the current state of corruption in Uzbekistan is due in many respects to the history of the genesis of this phenomenon in the country. Corruption phenomena have very deep roots, and at the initial stage of development they are inextricably linked with the bureaucracy and its officials as a tool for resolving the dilemma between unmet human needs and the absence of real mechanisms for their achievement. As a result of the analysis of the genesis of the phenomenon of corruption in the administrative law doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to determine the main difficulties in the formation of a unified national anti-corruption doctrine in historical retrospect:

- the imperfection of the terminological base as a prerequisite for an inadequate assessment of the severity and scale of corrupt activities;
- uneven assessment of the danger of corruption for some areas of the existence of the state and reassessment - for others.

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